

ISic0116

I.Sicily inscription 0116

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Original findspot not recorded; first observed fixed to the town hall of Termini

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 91

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 27 cm

Width 34 cm

Depth 16 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Musice

2. Viboniensis

3. ann(orum) · XXVI

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Musice, from Vibo (Valentia?), aged 26

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285207

EDR 126999

EDCS 22100066

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7365 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650797>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 34

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49 and tav.18.27

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